

POLICY BRIEF – OCTOBER 2024

CONCEPTUAL BASIS OF SUSTAINABLE DIGITALISATION

Abstract

The digitalisation of our societies is transforming our world. As a result, people's routines and ways of life are redefined through economic, environmental, social and governance domains. To some extent, it is unclear who will benefit from changes caused by digitalisation, and how, especially in the long term. In CODECS, we aim at shedding light on how socio-economic benefits will be distributed and redistributed and identifying ways of ensuring social, environmental, and economic sustainability with digitalisation. The CODECS conceptual framework operates in an ever-changing contextual situation in the agricultural sector in Europe. External drivers (e.g., social, technical, environmental, and political drivers) and internal drivers (e.g., capabilities, motivations and opportunities) influence entities, relationships and activities in different ways across different contexts. CODECS responds to this by applying a 'system thinking' approach to digitalisation levels. Three interconnected digitalisation levels are core to the CODECS conceptual framework: 1) Business processes, 2) Digital ecosystems, and 3) Socio-ecological systems. By distinguishing between different levels of digitalisation, the CODECS conceptual framework enables the necessary understanding of how to ensure acceleration of sustainable digitalisation through policymaking to influence change, by for instance, focusing on boosting the abilities of those involved and ensuring resources are sustained, accessible and fairly distributed.

1. Introduction

The world is in transition due to the digital transformation of our societies, and agriculture is no exception. Digital technologies make it possible to automate processes, which have resulted in opportunities that were unthinkable some years back. These advancements are made possible due to the representation of the physical world through numbers. For example, large datasets can be obtained by using sensors. The use of sensors in precision agriculture provides opportunities to gain large amounts of information on the spatial and temporal variation in crops, soil, weeds, diseases, etc. A wide range of sensors exist that can be used for different purposes, including satellite data for precision agriculture, crop data for improved harvests, soil data for water optimisation, livestock data for improved animal health, and disease and weed detection in crops for improved yields.

Digitisation is "the technical conversion of analogue information into digital form", or in other words "a process of representing the physical world through numbers". Digitisation has led to the third industrial revolution, which results from computers providing opportunities to the automated processes, leading to increased effectiveness in the use of inputs and enhanced profitability of outputs. This has been followed by the fourth industrial revolution, 'digitalisation'. With digitalisation, people's routines and way of life are redefined according to the digital

Funded by
the European Union

CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement n. 101060179. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

transformation of new economic, environmental, social and governance domains. The process of digital transformation is referred to as digitalisation.

Whereas digitisation opens ways to digital transformation by reorganising physical, social, and digital relationships in positive ways, it is unclear what possible long-term negative consequences this will have on the environment and societal inequalities. The analyses to date are often simplistic and analysing only linear relationships. Such analyses suffer from not including factors that may be explanatory for sustainability. In a systems approach, multiple relations, interdependencies, and feedback loops are included, and more real findings with factors influencing sustainability can be identified. Systems thinking offers ideas on how to investigate influences across and between factors and does not simply look at linear evaluation approaches.

The main aim of CODECS is to achieve sustainable digitalisation. This policy brief presents a CODECS conceptual framework that addresses the main interrelationships in a system with three levels are taken into account in observing digital transformation. This is to improve the understanding of the potential costs and benefits of digitalisation and to create a solid basis for decision-making that can enhance transformation towards sustainable digitalisation. Motivated by the risks associated with digitalisation, including an increase in societal inequalities, CODECS supports the following definition: **Sustainable digitalisation is a process of social transformation by which digital technologies are embodied into socio-economic life to promote intra-generational, inter-generational, inter-species wellbeing, reduce inequalities, and improve the health of ecosystems.**

2. The CODECS conceptual Framework

The CODECS conceptual framework operates in an ever-changing contextual situation, impacted by external drivers, such as social, technical, environmental, and political drivers, as well as internal drivers, such as capabilities, motivations and opportunities. The contextual factors include entities, relationships, and activities. The framework is exploratory and gives an overview of how to systematically link digital technologies in transitions to sustainable digitalisation through a lens fit to a context with complexities, multiple dimensions, feedback loops, and rebound effects (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 – CODECS conceptual framework

The CODECS conceptual framework begins with the farm enterprise- or farmers' needs and their digitalisation transition through the business processes, digital ecosystem and Social Ecological System (SES) levels. At each level, the digitalisation impacts cover a larger scope in terms of more involved numbers of people, larger geographical area, more changes of behaviours and increase in use of technologies. With this increase in outreach and scope of digitalisation, the impacts on the economic, environmental, social and governance domains will increase. In addition, the context is changing. This illustrates that estimated costs and benefits of sustainability impacts at a certain step, period and context, can be changing over time, and differ across areas. The advancement of the transition period must be understood, to identify the actual costs and benefits of digitalisation. This insight can assist taking actions that ensures transitioning towards sustainable digitalisation. In short:

- LEVEL 1.** At a digitised business level, a transition from a basic level with no digitisation (referred to as a socio-physical system level), has taken place. At a digitised business level (referred to as a socio-physical system level), which is concentrated around the farm activities, a transition from a basic level with no digitisation takes place. At this level, the external drivers interact with the farm socio-physical system, resulting in different costs and benefits across different business process contexts.
- LEVEL 2.** At a digital ecosystem level (also referred to as socio-cyber-physical system level), a transition has taken place advancing the business process level to more multifarious and stronger societal impacts of digitalisation. At this level, more people, businesses, geographical coverage, activities, and interactions are involved than at the digitised business level. With these advancements in digitalisation, change is impacted by contextual external and internal factors, which interact with digitalisation processes. The environmental, economic, and social costs and benefits will vary across contexts, timeframes, and across different levels.
- LEVEL 3.** At a Socio-Ecological Systems (SES) level, a wide reach of potential influences of digitalisation are accounted for, including complex natural ecosystems, societal inequalities, and governance of our societies. The transformation has hence advanced. The SES level is also referred to as a transitioned socio-cyber-physical system level. At the SES level, interaction and outcomes appear within and across ecosystems, natural resources, governance and actor interactions.

3. Level 1: The business processes

CODECS begins with farmers' needs to analyse transitioning towards different levels of digitalisation. Thus, technologies for development of digitisation meet the needs of farmers and advance the basic level with no digitisation to a business processes level. Costs and benefits of the farm related processes can be analysed before and after digitisation, i.e. after the introduction of technologies. The business process level is where digital technologies deploy their effects, and it is at this level that, to date, the outputs and impacts of digitisation most frequently have been measured and analysed. Key elements of the business processes include:

- **Actors:** Human/animal components of the process.
- **Artifacts:** Physical components of the processes.
- **Activities:** Individual tasks or steps that make up a process.
- **Events:** Triggers or occurrences that initiate or conclude activities.
- **Gateways:** Decision points or branching paths in the process flow.
- **Flows:** Movement of information, materials, pollutions, or resources between activities or from/to the environment.
- **Resources:** Resources required to carry on the process.

Analyses of the changes introduced by digital technologies are typically based on the analyses of a) the system as-is, i.e. the business processes before the introduction of the technology; and b) the system to-be, i.e. after the introduction of the technology (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Business processes before and after organisation at farm level is digitised

The business process development depends on *readiness processes, defined by capabilities, motivations and opportunities at the farm level*. Optimal user readiness for digital technology is located at the overlap of capability, opportunity, and motivation (COM-components)¹.

4. Level 2: The digital ecosystem

At the second transitioning level in the CODECS conceptual framework, digital ecosystems are defined as **dynamic systems where digital, socio-economic, organisational, knowledge, and physical components converge to support the production, storage, communication, and utilisation of digital technologies and data**. A digital ecosystem supports the digitalisation of processes at the farm level by means of costs and benefits of connectivity infrastructures, organisational resources, human resources, knowledge, data, and platforms. With digitalisation, the reach of impacts of digital ecosystems extends networks of people, knowledge (e.g. the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS)), users of technologies, and changing behaviours. The impacts depend on the system readiness factors in the specific digital ecosystem. The digital ecosystem is judged “conductive” if it is successfully providing the benefits of these services. The core external drivers characterising digital ecosystems are summarised in Table 1.

Digital ecosystems are ecosystems where digital technologies mediate and affect the relationships among entities to perform a vast array of functionalities. Notably, a digital ecosystem has also been explained as a social system which needs to deal with heterogeneity and greater variations of actors’ abilities and resources to participate in a network. The digital ecosystem entails interconnected and intra-dependant digital platforms, created at key institutional levels (international, national and local/community) augmented by technical (ICT) and social networking processes. In the context of knowledge transfer and learning, a digital ecosystem can provide knowledge creation, recreation, diffusion, absorption, and exchanges that support the dynamics of social innovation.

Table 1 – External drivers characterising digital ecosystems

External drivers	Characteristics linked to the ecosystems
Social/ cultural	Trust, cooperation, communication, conflict resolution

¹ McCampbell, M., Adewopo, J., Klerkx, L., Leeuwis, C. (2023). Are farmers ready to use phone-based digital tools for agronomic advice? Ex-ante user readiness assessment using the case of Rwandan banana farmers. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 29(1), 29-51.

External drivers	Characteristics linked to the ecosystems
Technical/ technological	Connectivity, interoperability, intensity of data flows
Economic/ financial	Transaction costs, power distribution, trust
Environmental	Ecosystem integrity, diversity, connectivity
Political	Community of values and interests, institutional cohesion

5. Level 3: The Socio-Ecological System (SES)

At the third level, the Ostrom framework of socio-ecological systems (SES) is integrated in the CODECS conceptual framework. The transitioning from the digital ecosystems (a socio-cyber-physical system) level to the SES level (a transitioned socio-cyber-physical system) is encountering an ever-larger reach of costs and benefits. At this level, analyses of costs and benefits of digital technologies and interactions between human activity-based processes and natural resources are assessed at a more advanced level of digitalisation. The reach of digitalisation can be observed throughout the whole of Ostrom’s SES approach, covering the sustainability of natural resources and environmental ecosystems, as well as the governance, actors and capability dimensions.

The Ostrom SES framework consists of different subsystems with variations within these subsystems (Figure 4). The subsystems are categorised as resource systems, resource units, governance systems, and actors, who interact in so-called Focal Action Situations (FAS’s). Outcomes depend on these system interactions, including feedback loops. This system thinking can help to understand how the different factors impact real-world situations, including legal, economic, technological, political, social, and psychological components. The SES can examine situations where people interact with rules and norms repeatedly, guiding their decisions and actions.

Figure 3 – The Ostrom socio-ecological system (SES). Outcomes depend on interactions of resource and governance system, units and actors

6. Policy implications

This policy brief focuses on supporting sustainable digitalisation. Given the limited knowledge available about the actual reduction of negative social and environmental effects of digitalisation, CODECS presents in this policy brief a conceptual framework to account for the complexities involved in using a system thinking approach to facilitate the understanding of short- and long-term costs and benefits with digitalisation. CODECS uses systems thinking when addressing the costs and benefits of digitalisation, covering economic, environmental, and social costs and benefits. CODECS intends to assist in making a significant contribution to establish a basis for development, implementation, and evaluation of sustainability- and data-related policies at regional, national and EU levels. Moreover, CODECS has the ambitions to provide support to related objectives, including Green Deal ambitions, the new CAP, and the fair data sharing and exchanges through Common European Data Spaces, among others, as in the 2030 Digital Compass.

Digitalisation is a consequence of ever-improving smartness in the use of huge amounts of relatively cheap data to effectively support farmer's activities, with Artificial Intelligence (AI) expected to change opportunities drastically in the near future, with human behaviours and system interactions resulting in costs and benefits that can be unexpected. With the CODECS conceptual framework, we specify the transitioning across different levels of digitalisation. When digitalisation reaches levels beyond the primary intentions of adopting new technologies e.g., at the business level, people within the society adapt their behaviours in various ways, and in turn, environmental conditions and ecosystem cycles are eventually impacted by the changing human behaviours. Core societal impacts, including social inequalities and negative environmental impacts, e.g. climate change hazards, water scarcity, and biodiversity loss, will become issues of urgency if the European policy strategies are not acting and taking the necessary measures in time.

The CODECS framework suggests that digitalisation requires specific strategies that articulate the intervention at the three levels and tailor it to their specificity.

At the level of business processes, measures such as support to investments, agri-environmental schemes, and training programs should improve farmers' capabilities, their quality of life, and their production of public goods. This level requires a deep understanding of the diversity of farmers' readiness concerning the context where they live, to their structural characteristics, and to their transformative potential of digital solutions. Costs and benefits at this level should consider the return on public investment in digital technologies, as well as the spillover effects in terms of learning and innovation.

The digital ecosystem provides the resources necessary to activate the potential of digital technologies at the farm level. At this level, connectivity infrastructures, data-sharing schemes, platforms, advisory services, research and innovation policies should be considered. Also, policies addressing the existing AKIS should consider how digitalisation affects the relations between advisory services, research, technology providers, training and education.

The socio-ecological system (SES) is the level where social, economic, and environmental sustainability is assessed in a broader context. Addressing digitalisation at this level entails considering how the governance influences patterns of natural resources and the overall societal norms to allow consistency of using digital technologies and adopting sustainable management of resource systems. Policy tools at this level - for example, land use, water policies, biodiversity strategies, but also technology-related policies such as data and AI regulation - should take into account the role digitalised agricultural practices can play in the sustainable management of these resources, as well as the risk of introducing non-appropriate technologies.

To accelerate sustainable digitalisation through policymaking, it is crucial to focus on boosting the abilities of those involved and ensuring resources are sustained, accessible and fairly distributed.

When setting priorities, it is key to identify which actors could enhance the system's performance with policymaking and recognise how governance system changes can aid resource creation and capability improvement. CODECS suggests that innovation policies should seek a balance between technical, institutional, and technological advancements. Digital readiness requires that users are comfortable with the technology, have access to necessary hardware and software, and possess the skills and knowledge to use them effectively. Acknowledging digital readiness as a major drive to extend transitions towards sustainable digitalisation across Europe is vital and plays a pivotal role in adapting to higher digitalisation levels.

With the CODECS conceptual framework, a system's understanding of potential costs and benefits will improve substantially. A clearer understanding of the socio-cyber physical system level (i.e., in the CODECS conceptual framework) in future policy implementation will likely enhance sustainable digitalisation. In CODECS, scientific insights will be derived about costs and benefits across a total of 20 living labs distributed across Europe. In addition, CODECS will focus on selected topics in-depth on a larger scale such as increased inequalities and digital divide, inclusion of women in digitisation, and biodiversity. CODECS desires to trigger the transition towards the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by enhancing social, environmental and economic benefits at all levels and reducing costs. To contribute to more insights into social, economic and environmental costs and benefits of digitalisation, relevant research questions remain, such as:

- Do the existing digitalisation trends in agriculture correspond to the sustainable digitalisation criteria?
- How should the costs and benefits of sustainable digitalisation of agriculture in the near and far future be measured and distributed?
- How should the different dimensions of sustainability when promoting the digitalisation of agriculture be conciliated?

Authors: KATRINE SOMA (WR), GIANLUCA BRUNORI (UNIFI), CYNTHIA GIAGNOCAVO (UAL), ANDREA KNIERIM (UNI-HOHENEIM), DANIELE VERGAMINI (UNIFI), ROSA MARIA HEREDIA HORTIGÜELA (UAL), ALESSIO FERRARI (CNR), CHIARA MANNARI (CNR), MANLIO BACCO (CNR), TROND SELNES (WR), ELISA CIRAVEGNA (WR), LIVIA ORTOLANI, (UNIFI), TIZIANA NADALUTTI (UNIFI), ALEXIA GOBRECHT (INRAE), VERONIQUE BELLON-MAUREL (INREA), CONSTANTINE ILIOPOULOS (ELGO-DEMETER), REINOUT GODAERT (EV-ILVO), MARK RYAN (WR)

Email: katrine.soma@wur.nl

More info: www.horizoncodecs.eu

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18743658

**Funded by
the European Union**

CODECS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement n. 101060179. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.